

Three New Nothogenera in Cactaceae

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Abstract—The nothogenera *×Chamageocereus*, *×Feroleinia* and *×Xhonneuxara* are proposed.

×Chamageocereus M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**

= *Chamaecereus* Britton & Rose × *Haageocereus* Backeb.

= *×Haagivia* M.van der Meer

= *×Chamygmaecereus* Mordhorst

×Feroleinia M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**

= *Ferocactus* Britton & Rose × *Kroenleinia* Lodé

Ferocactus schwarzii G.E.Linds. × *Kroenleinia grusonii* (Hildm.) Lodé

= *×Echinoferocactus* P.V.Heath

×Xhonneuxara M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**

= *Coryphantha* (Engelm.) Lem. × *Ferocactus* Britton & Rose × *Leuchtenbergia* Hook.

Coryphantha elephantidens Lem. × *×Ferobergia* Glass cv. [= *Ferocactus* sp. ×
Leuchtenbergia principis Fisch. ex Hook.]

Named for Belgian botanist Guy Marie Xhonneux Dewolf.

